

A global analysis of the Operation and Maintenance role on the placing of wave energy farms

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Abstract

In this work an analysis of suitable locations for the development of wave energy farms is carried out based on representative operation and maintenance parameters. The analysis is applied globally on the basis of long-term global climate data set. Availability and accessibility levels are assessed first by considering different wave height thresholds. Secondly, the O&M access limits are quantified in terms of the weather windows and waiting period between them considering different windows lengths and scenarios. Finally, the O&M cost per kWh is calculated for a wave energy converter based on a point absorber concept. O&M costs has been calculated following the methodology proposed on Guanche et al 2014. As expected, results show that locations with mild wave climate have very low O&M costs per kWh. Some areas with high wave resource, such as Scotland, Spain or Nova Scotia present reasonable O&M costs compared to the power production in these areas. However, other locations with high resource like Chile or Australia resulted in extremely high O&M costs due to the inaccessibility of these sites during long periods of time.

Keywords: Operation and maintenance, weather window, O&M, wave energy

1. INTRODUCTION

Wave energy converters (WEC) are still at a prototype testing stage. Some countries are promoting wave energy conversion by dedicated investments or special feed in tariffs. However, there are just few regions in the world where WEC prototypes have been tested offshore.

When assessing WEC installation sites, developers usually aim for sites with the highest wave energy resource. Consequently, countries like Scotland, Ireland or Portugal have made important efforts to incorporate the high untapped potential of this energy source to their energy mix.

However, high wave energy resource is usually linked to rougher sea conditions. Therefore, the selection of a location for the deployment of a WEC is highly dependent on the deployment, operation and maintenance activities and should be accounted for in the assessment process. One of the primary causes of unsuccessful marine operations is due to poor marine conditions. According to the International Energy Agency one of the key issues related with offshore marine energy is the shortage of suitable deployment vessels for adverse weather conditions and the long time that should be waited for the maintenance operations. In the case of offshore wind energy, wind turbines could be deployed in areas with high wind resource but "mild" wave conditions. However in the case of WECs, both resource to be harvested and conditions for repair are completely correlated, so the site assessment should be carried out looking for a balance between both.

The research carried out in (O'Connor, et al., 2013) and (O'Connor, et al., 2012) led to the conclusion that accessibility and availability factors have a significant impact with respect the financial return of wave energy technology. They concluded that intensive and high O&M costs should be expected in locations with adverse climate. These O&M costs have an impact of about a 30% of the total cost of the WEC. A method for the assessment of weather windows in order to manage marine operations was presented in (Walker, et al., 2011). They concluded that the primary influencing factor that affects O&M costs is related with the amount of available weather windows on a particular location, so this is an important point when choosing the deployment location of a wave energy project. With respect to the geospatial analysis of wave energy deployment constraints in the analysis carried out in UK waters of (Nobre, et al., 2009) seven criteria were considered for choosing a suitable area for energy conversion: sea bottom geology, distance to shore, ports and power grid, average wave height, period and power. There are no studies related with the optimum location for wave energy development from a worldwide perspective, taking into account the O&M costs. This paper presents a study of the suitability for wave energy development from a global perspective with emphasis on O&M costs. This paper has been structured as follows: first, the wave climate database will be described; second, the availability and accessibility indicators around the world will be shown; third, the O&M main parameters (weather windows and waiting period between weather windows) will be presented; finally, the worldwide influence of the O&M costs on the energy cost will be analyzed for a WEC composed by a set of heaving cylinders (Andres.A., et al., 2014).

2. METHODOLOGY

For the global analysis of weather windows and their durations, a long-term global meteocean database is required. For this study, the global reanalysis database (GOW 1.0) from (Reguero, 2012) and (Espejo, et al., 2011) is used. GOW 1.0 is based on the NCEP/NCAR reanalysis atmospheric forcing (Kalnay, et al., 1996), which constitutes one of the longest global wind reanalysis. GOW 1.0 database provides hourly spectral sea state parameters: significant wave height (H_s), mean period (T_m), peak period (T_p) and mean direction (θ_m) as well as the directional spectra components $S(f, \theta)$ for the period 1948-2008, with $1^\circ \times 1.5^\circ$ global coverage. For this study, 1188 nodes along the world shoreline with an average spacing of 200 km have been selected (Espejo, 2011) with water depths ranging from 50 m to 100 m.

In this work O&M is assessed by means of indicators including some representative sea state parameters. According to (O'Connor, et al., 2012) and (Walker, et al., 2011) the main parameters to be considered are the following:

- Significant wave height (H_s) is the most important parameter considering the fact that O&M activities are usually limited by this parameter. According to (O'Connor, et al., 2012) there is a limiting working wave height depending on the type of vessel used for the operation and the type of offshore structure to be boarded (wind turbine, WEC...). For offshore wind turbines the range of operating wave heights ranges from 1.5 m for Catamarans to 3 m using the Amplemann system. For WECs, the range of wave height limit is about 1.5 or 2 m according to (O'Connor, et al., 2013).
- Peak period (T_p): according to (Walker, et al., 2011) there is a range of operating periods for each type of barge. Normally, the limiting periods for usual barges for O&M activities range from 4 to 16 s depending on the relative direction between barge and wave propagation direction.
- Other parameters as wind speed or current speed are important in order to study the access limits for the different vessel types. According to (O'Connor, et al., 2013) the wind speed access limits vary between 8 m/s to 15 m/s.

Finally, O&M cost can be calculated. Based Guanche et al 2014 an O&M cost long term assessment has been carried out.

3. RESULTS

3.1.- Accessibility and Availability.

Two indicators are crucial in understanding the relation between WEC operation and weather conditions: availability and accessibility. Availability is the percentage of time that a WEC (or turbine in the case of wind energy for instance) is ready to produce electricity. This parameter is dependent on met-ocean conditions and type of converters. Regarding the converter typology, each WEC has a wake up threshold, an operational range and a survival mode. However, due to the absence of long term deployments the information about the thresholds levels is scarce. For instance, according to (Rashid & Hasanzadeh, 2011) the Pelamis enters into survival mode at a $H_s=8$ m whereas the C5-600 Wave Star prototype works up to $H_s=6$ m, see (Wavestar, 2015). According to (Saulnier, 2007) survival limits for SEAREV and AWS devices are reported to be $H_s= 8$ m and $H_s=6.5$ m, respectively. Even less information is available about

the wake up thresholds. In this work the wake up level is assumed to be $H_s = 0$ m. In this study, a conservative value of $H_s = 5$ m is set for the survival mode level.

Figure 1: Availability map in percentage for wave height threshold $H_s=5$ m

Figure 1 shows the percentage of time that WEC devices would be in the operational range along the world’s coastlines. As can be seen in the figure there are lot of coastal regions reaching almost a 100% availability, many of them corresponding to low resource areas. Some low availability-high wave energy resource areas are also visible, such as the east coast of Ireland and the south-east part of Chile. Although these areas could be of interest for their high resources, availability rates should be taken into account if a wave energy farms are to be developed since availability is about 80% with and additional 20% of the time in survival mode. In terms of operation it can be concluded that although some locations have an extremely high resource, due to the survivability limitations of the devices power cannot be extracted out of the most energy-rich sea states.

Thresholds	Availability (%)			
	<90%	90%-95%	95%-99%	99%-100%
$H_s < 5$ m	4%	6%	14%	76%
$H_s < 6$ m	0%	3%	12%	85%
$H_s < 8$ m	0%	0%	3%	97%

Table 1: Percentage of GOW coastal nodes on different availability levels.

Figure 2 shows the global average available power obtained for different survivability H_s thresholds. As can be seen some sites with very high resource (like the east coast of Ireland) have similar available resource as other areas with lower total resource (like the west coast of Portugal) when a lower wave height threshold is considered for the availability study. For completeness, Table 1 shows the percentage of coastal nodes in the GOW reanalysis that satisfy certain levels of availability. As can be seen, the availability is quite high for all the thresholds considered.

Wave energy resource (kW/m) with restriction on availability $H_s < 5m$

Wave energy resource (kW/m) with restriction on availability $H_s < 6m$

Wave energy resource (kW/m) with restriction on availability $H_s < 8m$

Figure 2: Wave energy restrictions with availability restrictions (kW)

Accessibility, defined as the percentage of the time when the device could be accessed for the maintenance operations, is the second relevant indicator. Accessibility is device specific too and depends both on the met-ocean conditions, the type of device and on the type of vessel used for the operations. As shown in (O'Connor, et al., 2012) wave height limits may vary from 1 m to 3 m depending on the type of specialized vessel. Figure 3 shows accessibility levels (in % of the year) assuming wave height to be the single variable defining accessibility. As can be seen, wave height thresholds play an important role in assessing the accessibility level and its spatial distribution. For instance, for a $H_s=1$ m threshold almost all coastal areas have low accessibility levels with values close to 30%. Only enclosed seas like the Mediterranean or the Baltic show much higher (nearly 80%) accessibility levels for this low H_s . However wave resource at those sites is limited.

For a $H_s=1.5$ m threshold, many locations show acceptable accessibility levels. For instance, in Europe, the accessibility indicator levels range from 68% in Denmark's North Sea coast, a 45 % in the Spanish or Portuguese north and west Atlantic coasts or 20% in the open Atlantic coasts of Ireland or Scotland. In the Pacific coasts of America, the accessibility levels range from almost 90% in Central America to a 30% to 40% in Canada and the USA coasts, to a 20% in Chile. If the threshold is increased to $H_s=2$ m the accessibility levels of some coastal areas change significantly as is the case for Europe, where the accessibility levels increase to a 60% in Spain and Portugal and to a 35 % in Ireland and Scotland. Under this threshold areas like Chile and the South coast of Australia still have very low accessibility levels (20%). For the East (Atlantic) coast of America the levels of accessibility are quite high, nearly reaching a 90%. Reducing the strictness of this threshold, a 3 m threshold would imply very high accessibility levels all around the globe. Except for some areas with extremely rough conditions including Ireland, Chile and southern Australia, a 90% or higher availability is reached almost everywhere.

Thresholds	Accessibility (%)			
	0-25%	25%-50%	50%-75%	75%-100%
	Percentage of nodes/ Mean Wave energy resource			
$H_s < 1\text{m}$	50% / 23 kW/m	20% / 9.35 kW/m	21% / 5 kW/m	9% / 2 kW/m
$H_s < 1.5\text{m}$	18% / 35 kW/m	24% / 18 kW/m	26% / 10 kW/m	32% / 4 kW/m
$H_s < 2\text{m}$	6% / 48 kW/m	12% / 30 kW/m	24% / 18 kW/m	58% / 7 kW/m
$H_s < 2.5\text{m}$	1% / 55 kW/m	7% / 42 kW/m	15% / 26 kW/m	77% / 9 kW/m

Hs<3m	0/ -----	2%/ 53 kW/m	11%/ 36 kW/m	83%/ 11 kW/m
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Table 2: Percentage of GOW reanalysis coastal nodes with the different accessibility levels

Table 2 shows the percentage of the GOW reanalysis coastal nodes corresponding to the range of accessibility levels for different Hs thresholds considered. As can be seen, for a wave height threshold of 1.0 m, 50% of the nodes have accessibility levels below 25% (very limited accessibility for O&M). As can be seen, the higher the wave height threshold, the lower the percentage of nodes with accessibility below a given value. For example, for the Hs=2.5 m threshold, 1% of the nodes have accessibility levels below 25% and 7% of the nodes reach values between 25% and 50%. Table 2 also includes the mean wave energy flux corresponding to the percentage of GOW coastal nodes that are on a given accessibility level range. It should be noticed that for the most restrictive thresholds the nodes with high accessibility (75%-100%) have very low resource (2 kW/m). From an economic perspective, in order to find a balance between resource, accessibility and number of locations satisfying the conditions specified in Table 2, the higher Hs thresholds are studied. For instance for the Hs=2 m threshold, the percentage of nodes with accessibility between 50% and 75% is 24% and the mean wave energy resource of these nodes is 18 kW/m. For Hs=2.5 m and Hs=3.0 m and the same accessibility level range, these values are 15% and 26 kW/m and 11% and 36 kW/m, respectively.

Figure 3: Accessibility (in %) for different wave height thresholds

Figure 4: Location of the sites chosen for further study.

After this global preliminary assessment, a more detailed analysis is carried out by selecting seven pilot regions namely: coastal areas northwest of Denmark, west of Ireland, Chile, north of Spain, west of Portugal, southwest of Australia and west of Scotland, see Figure 4. The regions chosen are part of countries

where a well-known interest in wave energy has been perceived in the last years. Table 3 summarizes key figures in terms of resource and accessibility at each site. It can be concluded that locations with very high resource (Chile and Australia) have very low accessibility levels. In the case of Australia for instance, even for the 3 m threshold, the accessibility is as low as 50%. In Chile, the accessibility is low too, but an abrupt change on accessibility is noticed from the 2 m to 2.5 m threshold since accessibility changes from 32% to 61% due to the differences on the wave height distributions. Consequently, sites with very similar resource, may show very different accessibility rates depending on wave height distribution functions. If the attention is focused on Ireland and the southern coast of Australia the differences are noticeable. Both locations have the same resource (62 kW/m), however the levels of accessibility for all thresholds are much higher in Ireland.

Locations	Longitude	Latitude	Mean wave energy resource without restrictions (kW/m)	Accessibility (%)				
				Hs<1	Hs<1.5	Hs<2	Hs<2.5	Hs<3
northwest of Denmark	7.5	57	12	44	64	77	85	90
west of Ireland	-10.5	53	62	7	19	34	47	59
Chile	-73.5	-36	34	1	9	32	61	81
north of Spain	-3	44	28	25	47	64	75	83
west-Portugal	-9	40	29.5	18	42	60	73	82
south of Australia	115.5	-35	62	0.01	1	10	29	51
west Scotland	-4.5	59	50	8	23	38	52	64

Table 3. Accessibility levels (in percentage) for the selected locations and the selected thresholds

Locations like Denmark, with a low wave energy resource, show very high accessibility levels. There are also some intermediate situations, like Spain and Portugal that have similar resource (about 30 kW/m) and accessibility levels ranging from 25% for the 1 m threshold to 83% for the 3 m threshold. The case of Scotland should also be highlighted. The wave energy resource here is high (50 kW/m), whereas the levels of accessibility are low (8% for the 1 m threshold and 64% for 3 m).

Figure 5: Mean monthly accessibility for Denmark, Ireland, Chile and Spain

It should also be noticed how Ireland and Australia have the same average resource (62 kW/m), while the levels of accessibility are extremely different for all the thresholds.

In order to account for seasonality, monthly accessibility levels are analyzed at each region. Figure 5 and Figure 6 show the monthly accessibility curves for each location and every wave height thresholds. As expected, results show much lower accessibility during the winter than during the summer months. Also sites closer to the Equator (for instance Chile) show smaller variability in the winter-summer accessibility levels than the locations that are at higher latitudes. In the case of Denmark it can be seen that its accessibility levels are medium to high even during the winter months. For $H_s=1.5$ m the accessibility during the winter months is about a 45%, high compared to other locations.

It should be highlighted that in Chile, accessibility has a stronger dependency on the thresholds than the rest of the locations. In contrast, Australia with very similar wave energy resource shows a stronger seasonal dependency due to milder summers than in Chile. Wave height distribution at this particular site is significantly different from the Chilean site, and even with a similar resource both sites are very different from a strategic wave energy development point of view. However, Chile shows a very low seasonal variations because a reduced storminess results in relatively steady wave conditions along the year. This

fact is positive for wave energy development in Chile, since failures are expected to occur during the winter time with a lower probability during the rest of the year, allowing a better, more regular and planned maintenance.

Figure 6: Monthly accessibility for Portugal, Scotland and Australia

European Atlantic locations (Scotland, Ireland, Spain and Portugal show a similar behavior for all thresholds. Differences on accessibility between winter and summer months are high and dependent on the Hs threshold level chosen. Focusing on winter months (where O&M activities are most probable because of failures) the differences are high among the different locations. For instance for Hs=2 m the accessibility levels are 40% for Spain, 15% for Ireland, 38% for Portugal and 15% for Scotland. This means that winter accessibility levels in Ireland and Scotland are very low. Therefore, there will be long periods of inaccessibility during winter time when maintenance operations will be imposible. This fact has two main implications: 1) if a failure occurs and corrective maintenance is not possible during a long time period then the converter should be in survival mode and will not produce energy and 2) the lack of maintenance could result in increasing damage for the the device during the inaccessibility period.

From Table 3 and Figure 5 and Figure 6 it can be concluded that there are some locations with high energy potential and harsh sea conditions (for instance Australia, Ireland or Scotland) where, if a wave energy

converter is deployed, reliability of the WEC should be very high in order to avoid failures and the corresponding corrective maintenance during winter months. In these sites the maintenance strategy should be focused on preventive maintenance during the summer months, when accessibility levels reach 60%. However, wave energy is still at a prototype testing stage and WECs have not been exposed to offshore conditions during long periods of time to assure high reliability levels.

Other regions have high accessibility and low wave energy resource, such as Denmark and are less dependent on O&M. A last group of locations such as Spain and Portugal are characterized by medium wave energy resource and acceptable accessibility levels during the winter months (about 40% for $H_s=2$ m, 220% higher than in Ireland or Scotland) providing an excellent location for the deployment of WEC farms based solely on these criteria.

3.2.-Weather window and waiting period analysis

In the previous section the WEC availability and accessibility around the coasts of the world has been analyzed. However O&M is also strongly dependent on weather windows characteristics since O&M activities requires a certain time interval to be carried out. For instance, based on DONG energy experience, at the Borkum offshore wind farm (located in the North Sea, around 57 Km from the Netherlands shores) a weather window of 12 h is needed for a 6 h of effective maintenance work time.

The analysis carried out in this section is focused on the influence of the wave height on the O&M activities; nevertheless this study could have been also applied similarly to deployment and decommissioning procedures. Apart from wave height there are other variables affecting O&M such as wind speed, tides, wave period, etc. that have not been taken into account in this work but for a global study wave height has been considered to have a first order effect compared to the others. Keeping that issue in mind, a common, conservative $H_s=1.5$ m threshold has been chosen based on (Abdulla, et al., 2011) and (O'Connor, et al., 2013). For each wave reanalysis node the annual number of weather windows of at least 6 h, 12 h and 24 h duration were calculated. As the GOW is a 60 year reanalysis database, 60 values were obtained at each node. Then mean and the standard deviation of the number of weather windows per year are represented in Figures 7 to 9. It should be pointed out that for this analysis the number of consecutive periods of x hours weather windows has been considered. Then for instance if there is a period of 36 h with accessible weather conditions 6 weather windows of 6 h, 3 of 12 h and 1 of 24 h will be considered with the applied criteria.

3.2.1.- Annual number of weather windows analysis.

Figure 7 shows the number of 6 h weather windows per year. It should be noticed that the maximum number of 6 h weather windows per year is 1460. Maps show that these high values can be found in some areas such as the Mediterranean or the China Sea characterized by a large accessibility and low resource.

Figure 7: Average and standard deviation of the number of 6 h weather windows per year

Some areas in Europe have 300 weather windows per year on average but in regions such as the Atlantic coast of Ireland and the west coast of South America this number drops down to a very low number of weather windows, namely about 100. The Argentinian coast, the southern coast of Brasil and the coasts of Nova Scotia in Canada present high annual mean values, 1200 in Argentina and about 1000 in Nova Scotia. A remarkable latitudinal variability is found in the Pacific along the west coast of America ranging from 300 at the California Peninsula, increasing to 1200 in the west coast of Central America and dropping back to about 100 at the Chilean coast.

The lower panel in Figure 7 shows the standard deviation of the annual number of weather windows. The maximum standard deviation is near 200 per year. Locations with the highest variability correspond usually to locations with high number of weather windows. The Chilean coast, as well as the south coast of Australia show the lowest weather windows variability. In Europe the standard deviation found in the

Mediterranean coasts is of the order of 50 weather windows per year, very similar to the one in the Irish west coast. However, the ratio between standard deviation and the mean (coefficient of variation) shows that both sites have a very different performance, Irish waters showing a higher variation coefficient than the Mediterranean. It is also remarkable that the west coast of India has a high standard deviation, about 200 compared with its mean, 700. Also two areas with a very similar mean number of annual weather windows, have very different standard deviations, namely about 200 for the Guinean Gulf and as little as 50 for the Mediterranean. This means that the variability of the accessibility in the Gulf is much higher than in the Mediterranean.

Figure 8: Average and standard deviation of the number of 12 h weather windows per year

In Figure 8 the number of weather windows with a 12 h duration is studied. In this case a full year accessibility corresponds to 730 weather windows. It can be seen that the number of locations with full availability is lower than for the 6 h windows case. Comparing maps it should be noticed that the number of nodes with weather window accessibility higher than 80% (calculated as the number of weather windows divided by the maximum number of weather windows on a year) is 25% for the 6 h windows case whereas for the 12 h weather windows this percentage is lowered to 20%.

Regarding the number of weather windows for this particular case, it is very similar to the 6 h map and the only difference is that the areas with lowest and highest number of weather windows are highlighted in the 12 h map and then the differences are increased.

Finally, Figure 9 shows the maps corresponding to weather windows of 24 h duration. For this case the maximum possible number of weather windows per year is 365. As expected the number of locations with high number of weather windows is reduced. Only 15% of the locations have accessibility values higher than 80%. Geographically the distribution of weather windows resembles the 6 h and 12 h maps. Moreover, as shown at the lower panel of the figure, standard deviations for the 24 h window case has a similar geographic distribution to the one found for the 6 h and 12 h weather windows.

Figure 9: Average and standard deviation of the number of 24 h weather windows per year

Table 5 shows the number of weather windows having $H_s < 1.5$ m for selected sites focused on wave energy. Denmark is the location with the highest average number of 6-hour weather windows, 904 from a maximum of 1460. Spain and Portugal have a very similar number of weather windows, about 600. For Scotland and Ireland the average number of weather windows is close to 300. It should be pointed out that Australia almost doubles the number 6 h weather windows when compared to Chile. However, for 24 h windows the number is almost the same. This means that the continuity of the weather windows is lower in Australia than in Chile, as Chile's seasonality is much lower than Australia's seasonal variation. For Denmark and

Spain the standard deviation of the number of weather windows is very similar for all cases. However, the average number of windows is higher for Denmark. This means that Denmark has higher accessibility and variation of this accessibility than North of Spain.

3.2.2.- Waiting period analysis

Being one of the most important variables in order to plan an O&M strategy, periods of inaccessibility are also assessed in this section. Once a failure occurs at an offshore structure, a maintenance operation is needed, and it will only take place once the maintenance team has an available weather window.

As suggested by (O'Connor, et al., 2013) the periods of inaccessibility are more probable to occur during winter months. The waiting period is defined then as the period of time among weather windows (that satisfy a certain wave height threshold for this case) of at least certain duration. The weather window definition is taken as in the previous subsection (dividing the database in periods of x hours).

Individual waiting periods among weather windows of a given duration (6 h, 12 h and 24 h) and their mean, standard deviation and 99% quantile values are calculated for each year of the 60-years GOW database. From these 60 values, the total mean waiting period, the mean standard deviation and the mean 99% quantile are calculated.

In Figure 10 the waiting period parameters are shown for the weather window of at least 6 h. On the top panel the mean waiting period is represented. On this map many areas have waiting periods of less than 1 day. In the European coastlines differences among areas are relatively low. The Mediterranean or Denmark have waiting periods 0.3 days long on average, while this value reaches about 1.2 days at the West Irish coast.

Figure 10: Mean, mean standard deviation and mean 99% quantile waiting period during winter time for a weather window of at least 6 h

The areas with highest mean waiting periods correspond to the Chilean coast as well as to the South coast of Australia. Apart from these areas with high mean waiting periods the majority of the areas around the East and West coast of America are noticed by waiting periods lower than 2 days.

In the middle panel the mean standard deviation of the waiting period is plotted. Differences in the European coasts are here reinforced. Whereas the Mediterranean coasts have mean standard deviations lower than 2 days, the West coast of Ireland presents standard deviations of 6 days. This fact highlights the variability of the waiting periods in the Atlantic coast of Ireland and UK, and it also demonstrates the high variability between summer and winter. As expected the areas with a higher variability are the Chilean coast and the Southern part of Australia with standard deviations of 18 and 10 days, respectively.

In the bottom panel of Figure 10 the mean 99% quantile of the waiting period is shown, providing an indicator of the extreme waiting periods that normally occur in winter. In this case the differences among the different areas in the world are much more evident. Low 99% waiting period quantiles correspond to the Mediterranean, the West coast of Central America, as well as to the East coast of South America and the majority of the locations in the Indian Ocean. All these locations present a mean 99% quantile of less than 10 days. Conversely, the Atlantic coast of Ireland is characterized by very high 99% waiting period quantiles, around 30 days. Chile and South of Australia present, as expected, very high 99% waiting period quantiles, reaching 86 and 55 days, respectively.

Figure 11: Mean, mean standard deviation and mean 99% quantile waiting period during winter time for a weather window of at least 12 h

In Figure 11 the mean, mean standard deviation and the mean 99% quantile waiting periods for the 12 h weather window are represented. The geographic distribution is very similar to the one obtained for the 6 h windows, the main difference being a general increase of the waiting period as the weather window increases. In general, for the 12 h weather window, the average waiting period is around twice the average weather window obtained for the 6 h weather window.

For the middle panel the mean standard deviation plot for the 12 h weather window resulted in a geographic distribution very similar to the 6 h weather window results. The mean 99 % waiting period quantile plot, at the bottom, shows almost the same geographic distribution as the 6 h weather window plots of Figure 10, although the most extreme areas are highlighted as explained in Table 4.

Figure 12: Mean, mean standard deviation and mean 99% quantile waiting period during winter time for a weather window of at least 24 h

In Figure 12 the mean, mean standard deviation and mean 99% of the waiting period for the 24 h weather window is shown. “Although geographically the plots are very similar to the 6 h and 12 h windows, the main difference is again a general increase of the average waiting period as the weather window increases. In general, for the 24 h weather window, the average waiting period is around five times the average weather window obtained for the 6 h weather window”.

The mean 99% waiting period quantile plot is again similar to the previous figures. Differences found between the 6 h, 12 h and 24 h plots are highlighted in Table 4 in which the percentage of nodes with mean and mean 99% quantile waiting periods of less than a given duration are calculated. As can be seen in this table, for a 6 h weather window 81% of GOW coastal nodes have a mean waiting period of less than 1 day. These percentages drop to 67% and 45% for 12 h and 24 h weather windows, respectively. This reduction in the percentage of nodes among the different weather windows is less dramatic if a less restrictive 7 days waiting period threshold is stated.

For the mean 99% waiting period, the 30 days threshold restriction is accomplished by 86% of the nodes if 6 h weather window are considered but only 60% of the nodes satisfy this condition for the 24 h weather windows. These relevant differences indicate the importance of a correct assessment of the duration of the weather window required for maintenance operation.

Parameters	Waiting period for a 6 h weather window	Waiting period for a 12 h weather window	Waiting period for a 24 h weather window
Average waiting period <1 days	81	67	45
Average waiting period <7 days	93	91	85
Quantile 99% waiting period <30 days	86	77	60
Quantile 99% waiting period <60 days	92	89	80

Table 4: Percentage of GOW reanalysis coastal nodes that satisfy a minimum waiting period

In Table 5 the results for the waiting period parameters for the selected locations are summarized. As can be seen in this table, the lowest waiting periods for all weather windows for the selected locations correspond to the West coast of Denmark, followed by the North coast of Spain and the Portugal coast.

Among the European sites, the West coast of Ireland and Scotland have the highest waiting period parameters in correspondence with their rough wave climate. For example, the West coast of Ireland has 30 days of waiting period for the 6 h weather window while the North coast of Spain has 8 days. Among

all the selected sites, the Southern coast of Australia and the Chile coast have the highest waiting periods. For example, for the 6 h weather window, the average waiting time in Chile is 86 days, nearly 3 times the Ireland’s one or 11 times more than in the North coast of Spain.

Locations	Number of Weather Windows per year			Waiting period (in days)		
	6h	12h	24h	6h	12h	24h
	Mean/Std	Mean/Std	Mean/Std	Mean/Std/Quantile99	Mean/Std/Quantile99	Mean/Std/Quantile99
North-West Denmark	904/ 79	436/ 39	203/ 20	0.15 / 1 / 4	0.34 / 1.4 / 7	0.8 / 2.51 / 13
West of Ireland	267/ 44	125/ 21	54/ 10	1.14/ 6 / 30	2.5 / 8 / 50	6 / 14 / 75
Chile	67/ 33	29/ 16	11/ 6	7/ 18 / 86	15.6 / 28 / 103	41 / 48 / 135
North of Spain	663/ 73	319/ 36	148/ 18	0.3/ 2 / 8	0.6/ 3 / 13	1.5/ 5 / 26
Portugal	586/ 67	282/ 33	129/ 17	0.4/ 2 / 10	0.8 / 3.4 / 16	1.85 / 6 / 30
Scotland	313/ 50	146/ 24	64/ 12	1/ 5 / 24	2 / 8 / 44	5 / 14 / 78
South of Australia	116/ 38	51/ 18	19/ 8	3.18/ 10 / 55	7 / 17 / 85	20 / 33 / 126

Table 5: Number of weather windows and duration of waiting periods (in hours) for the selected locations. Hs threshold: 1.5 m

Based on these figures it can be concluded that devices deployed in these areas (Chile, S. Australia, West Ireland or West Scotland) will require very high reliability levels, since the periods of inaccessibility in winter are very long preventing of any failures and/or maintenance during the winter months. This reliability is hard to achieve for wave energy prototypes due to their early development stages, making these locations less attractive for the testing of WEC prototypes due to risks associated with O&M.

Considering the mean 99% waiting period quantile, Australia and Chile show waiting periods between 2 and 4 months, depending on the weather window duration.

Respect to the mean standard deviation and the mean 99% quantile of waiting period, differences among locations are highlighted if the numbers in Table 5 are divided by the mean waiting period, see Table 6. As can be seen in this table, the waiting period variation parameters decrease as the weather window duration increases. Looking at the differences between locations, the variation parameters for South Australia and Chile are clearly lower than in the other locations that is one indication of a very stable wave climate produced by the swells coming from the “Roaring Forties” of the Southern Hemisphere. In the other extreme, the North coast of Spain has the highest variation coefficients due to the difference between the mild summer months and winter extreme storms, although all Europe countries show similar variation coefficients.

Waiting Period	6h			12 h			24 h		
	Mean	Sdv/M	99%/M	Mean	Sdv/M	99%/M	M	Sdv/M	99%/M
West Denmark	0.15	6.7	26.7	0.34	4.1	20.6	0.80	3.1	16.3
West of Ireland	1.14	5.3	26.3	2.50	3.2	20.0	6.00	2.3	12.5
Chile	7.00	2.6	12.2	15.60	1.8	6.6	41.00	1.2	3.3
North of Spain	0.30	6.7	26.7	0.60	5.0	21.7	1.50	3.3	17.3
Portugal	0.40	5.0	25.0	0.80	4.3	20.0	1.85	3.2	16.2
Scotland	1.00	5.0	24.0	2.00	4.0	22.0	5.00	2.8	15.6
South of Australia	3.18	3.1	17.3	7.00	2.4	12.1	20.00	1.7	6.3

Table 6. Mean waiting period, mean variation coefficient and mean 99% quantile/Mean waiting period for the three weather window and locations considered.

3.3.- Cost of Operation and Maintenance

In the previous sections the relevance of weather windows and waiting periods on maintenance operations has been analysed. As expected, locations with rougher wave climate have larger wave energy resource but also more difficult accessibility for maintenance. In this section the influence of O&M parameters on the energy cost is evaluated, trying to identify locations presenting a good balance between energy resource and availability for maintenance operations.

For this purpose a generic wave energy device, similar to the Wavestar device (Wavestar, 2011) is selected. The device is made of an array of floating cylinders attached to the main structure by an arm. In Andres et al. (2014) some modifications to the converter were analyzed in order to get the most cost-effective structure in terms of size. For the present study a cylinder with a diameter of 4 m is selected. The complete array is composed of 8 cylinders in two rows of four. The development of the power matrix is carefully explained in de Andres et al. (2014).

Based on the GOW wave data base, the global average wave power production is calculated and presented in Figure 13. As expected, the highest power production is located in Chile, north of Europe and south of Australia. However, these areas are characterized by rough climate conditions limiting O&M resulting in periods of inaccessibility that may hamper economic performance at these sites.

In this study only corrective maintenance has been considered. Preventive maintenance is characterized by a long term planning, most frequently scheduled during the summer months and may lead to erroneous conclusions on the assessment of how wave climate affects both productivity and feasibility. Consequently, this analysis is built upon a sequence of failure and corrective maintenance episodes assuming that, after

each failure, the maintenance team is ready to perform the required operations as soon as a weather window is available.

A random set of failures has been simulated along the years. When the failure occurs the waiting period starts counting until a weather window occurs. For consistency with previous sections, a wave height threshold of 1.5 m is chosen following O'Connor et al. (2012) and O'Connor et al. (2013). A required weather window of 6 h is also chosen following Abdulla et al. (2011) based on the experience gained with some WECs.

Figure 13: Average power production (kW)

The cost per kWh has been calculated dividing the cost of O&M by the harvestable power production during its life cycle. A detailed explanation of the O&M cost calculation methodology can be seen in Guanche et al. (2014). It should be noticed that this indicator was chosen in order to show the O&M with respect the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) (Eur/kWh). Energy cost has been calculated including the O&M considering the following combined hypothesis:

- The cost of the maintenance activities has been split up into three individual costs based on current available figures in industry:
 - A cost per hour while the vessel is waiting to start the maintenance activities (during the waiting period) of 625 Euros/h
 - A fixed cost referred to the mobilization of the vessel of 7000 Euros
 - A cost per hour while the device is being repaired of 1250 Euros/h
- During the waiting period and the weather window while the maintenance operation is happening the device is supposed to be stopped meaning that it is not producing energy (on survival mode).

Consequently, when a failure occurs the O&M cost will be calculated in Euros/kWh considering both the operation real cost and the loss of income for the time the device will not be producing energy. In the evaluation a random number of failures per year will be considered. The life cycle of the WEC is assumed to be 25 years. Considering the 60 year reanalysis database a bootstrapping technique, based on Espejo et al. (2011) and Guanche et al. (2014), is used in order to obtain 10.000 lifecycles 25 years each.

Failure is simulated like a random event along the year because although a failure is most probable to occur during wintertime, failure due to fatigue of primary structural elements or electrical and electronic components could happen at any time. This assumption provides a fair comparison if a global assessment is to be made. It is decided to fix the number of failures per year in order to study the influence of O&M in the energy cost.

Figure 14 shows the map of O&M costs divided by the energy production for 1, 3 and 5 failures per year, so 2 parameters (O&M cost and power production) influence this general cost of energy assessment.

At the top of the figure the map for the O&M costs for 1 failure per year is shown. As expected some areas (Mediterranean, Japan, east coast of North America) characterized by a very low resource, show very low O&M costs (0.5 Eurocents per kWh). This is due to the absence of periods of inaccessibility resulting in an immediate repair of the failure. Alternatively, sites with very high resource and very high power production (i.e. Chile or south coast of Australia) present a very low number of weather windows so that after a failure, the device could be stopped during a long time per year incurring in high O&M costs (more than 2 Eurocents/kWh). By comparing Figure 13 and 14 it can be pointed out that while Chile and Ireland have similar power productions, the O&M cost in Chile is three times higher than in Ireland. This is due to similar resource figures but very different accessibility levels. Similar O&M costs are encountered on the West coast of India, in this case due to the low available resource and intermediate waiting periods.

Some European locations show very good values for O&M costs, with, for instance, the north and west coasts of Spain and Portugal reflecting values around 0.5 Eurocents/kWh. Other locations like the coast of Nova Scotia have medium resource levels (around 25 kW/m) and low costs in terms of O&M (0.2 Eurocents/kWh). These kind of locations serve as a good example of an excellent combination of resource and availability. Also the northwest coast of Africa (Morocco) has low values for O&M costs (near 0.6 Eurocents/kWh) combined with an intermediate resource level.

Average cost of O&M in Eurocents/kWh for 1 failure per year

Average cost of O&M in Eurocents/kWh for 3 failures per year

Average cost of O&M in Eurocents/kWh for 5 failures per year

Figure 14: O&M cost in Eurocents/kW for 1,3 and 5 failures

Figure 14 also depicts results for 3 and 5 failures per year. As the number of failures increases the probability of distributing the failures along the year is higher. Consequently, locations with milder climates (Mediterranean, East coast of USA) have lower values of O&M costs compared to the rest locations. This is due to the fact that weather windows are available throughout the whole year. However, in locations where the climate is rougher weather windows are only available during summer reinforcing differences between locations.

In Figure 15, the mean and standard deviation of the O&M cost is shown for different selected locations. In the case of 1 failure per year (left panel in Figure 15), there are two locations, Australia and Chile that stand out for the high mean and standard deviation of O&M costs. This is due to the absence of weather windows during long periods, mainly in winter and. These locations show high O&M costs for all failure rates compared with the rest locations (for instance, 300% higher than in Spain), indicating that these locations would have more difficulties for wave energy development at early stages.

For European locations the lowest O&M cost corresponds to Denmark with 0.22 Eurocent/kWh. As explained before the availability in this location is around 65%, therefore, the combination between resource and availability gives a low cost of O&M. For higher number of failures the cost remains the lowest for these locations as the availability varies from 40% during winter months to 80% during summer months.

Figure 15: O&M cost for the different locations with 1,3 and 5 failures per year

Some locations like Ireland, 0.4 Eurocents/kWh, or Scotland, 0.6 Eurocents/kWh, present low values of O&M cost due to the high resource in these locations balanced with a medium to low availability. It should be highlighted that when the number of failures increases the cost of O&M is higher for Ireland (1.8 Eurocents/kWh) and 1.6 Eurocents/kWh in Scotland.

There are also some locations with a milder climate with good figures for the O&M cost. Spain and Portugal have a good combination between resource and availability with O&M costs of 0.57 Eurocents/kWh and 0.53 Eurocents/kWh, respectively. As failure rates get higher these locations present lower relative costs in comparison with more energy-rich locations (i.e. 1 Eurocents/kWh in Spain compared to the 1.6 Eurocents/kWh of Ireland for 3 failures per year). This is also due to the redistribution of failures along the year as the failure rate grows, and then locations like Portugal or Spain with high availability levels during summer (around 50%) achieve lower costs than more energy-abundant locations with lower availabilities (30% for summer months in Ireland for instance).

This fact proves that milder locations like Denmark, Spain or Portugal could be good for early stages of technology development. At these stages technologies are expected to have a higher failure rate, and then O&M cost is lower for these locations than the most energy-rich locations. Once a technology has reached its matureness and its failure rate is reduced, more energy-abundant locations, like Ireland, could be considered for deployment.

Figure 16: O&M cost (for 3 failures per year) and mean power production. Dk: West Denmark, Sp: North Spain, Pt: West Portugal, Sc: West Scotland, Ir: West Ireland, Au: South Australia, Ch: West Chile.

Finally, although locations with a mild climate have the lowest cost in terms of O&M, developers are interested in finding a balance between absorbed power and O&M. For this purpose Figure 16 is presented where the absolute O&M cost for 3 failures per year versus the mean power production is shown. The goal here is obtaining the location with the highest power production and the lowest cost in terms of O&M. As can be seen in Figure 16, the increase rate of O&M costs in terms of mean power production in the European locations is around 1.4 Eurocents/kW. This result is not surprising because all locations are under the track of the North Atlantic perturbations, with clearly defined relatively calm summers and stormy winters. As a fundamental hypothesis of the cost model is that the rate of failures is independent on the power production (in this case 3 failures per year) the increment of the wave severity in the Irish and Scotland areas only affect the O&M cost in the decrease of the number of weather windows and the increase of the waiting periods in such a way that the rate O&M cost/Mean Power Production is similar to other regions with milder wave climates as Spain or Portugal.

The case of Southern Australia and the West coast of Chile is clearly different. Here, the swells coming from the “Roaring Forties” produce wave heights over the threshold for maintenance operations all along the year. Although the mean power production is high, the low number of weather windows and high duration of the waiting periods, produce rates O&M cost/Mean Power Production around 3.4 for Australia and 5.0 for Chiles, two and near three times higher, respectively, than in the European waters.

Summing up, it can be concluded that:

All European locations selected can be considered as sites recommended for wave energy conversion. All of them have reasonable figures in terms of O&M. However some important differences must be highlighted:

- In the case of Denmark, both O&M cost and power production are low. The O&M costs stay significantly low with high failure rates due to high accessibility rates. Therefore, this location could be useful, for instance, for early development stages of new technologies. North Spain and Portugal present also good conditions for early stage developments.
- On the other hand, locations such as Ireland or Scotland have very high power production and the O&M cost is medium to low, increasing heavily with higher failure rates, due to low accessibility rates. This location is the most energy-rich one in the European set and highly recommendable for mature technologies with low failure rates.
- In addition, it could be inferred from the maps that there are some very good sites in terms of power production and O&M cost outside Europe. For instance, for 3 failures per year, the coast of Nova Scotia has a power production of 91 kW with an O&M cost of 100 Eurocent. This location represents a perfect balance between the resource and weather windows for O&M”
- Finally, locations submitted to the permanent high swells of the southern hemisphere will require very reliable and mature technologies or the development of maintenance systems that could be deployed with higher waves.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work a global analysis of the O&M main indicators is carried out. The met-ocean data is taken from a global reanalysis 60 year hourly database extracted from Reguero et al (2012). This database has a full coverage of the globe shoreline with 1188 grid nodes including hourly sea state parameters.

The availability and accessibility levels in different regions of the world are studied. It can be concluded that the accessibility has an extremely high dependency on the wave height threshold. For very restrictive thresholds (1 m or 1.5 m), accessibility in the regions with high resource (high latitudes) is very low (less than 20%). Hence, locations with very high resource (Chile and Australia) have very poor accessibility levels. In the case of Australia for instance, even for the 3 m threshold the accessibility is 50%, that is low for this limit. If attention is focused on Ireland and South Australia the differences are noticeable. Both

points have the same resource (62 kW/m), however the levels of accessibility for all thresholds are much higher in Ireland (60%).

There are also some intermediate situations, in the case of Spain and Portugal, both locations have a similar resource and accessibility levels. The mean wave energy resource is around 30 kW/m and the accessibility levels range from 25% for the 1 m threshold to the 83% at the 3 m threshold. Also in Scotland the wave energy resource is high (50 kW/m), however the levels of accessibility are low (from 8% at the 1 m threshold until 64% at the 3 m threshold). Regarding seasonality, the difference on accessibility between winter and summer months is high, almost doubled, depending on the threshold level chosen. In winter months, when O&M could be required because of failures, differences are high between the different locations. For instance, for a threshold of 2 m the accessibility levels are 40% for Spain, 15% for Ireland, 38% for Portugal and 15% for Scotland.

A study of persistence of weather conditions is performed next for the weather window and waiting period analysis. Large weather windows highlight the differences between mild and rough climate locations. From this study it is also concluded that the entire coastline around the Indic Ocean is hard in terms of high waiting periods. Also the West coast of South America is characterized by a low number of weather windows and waiting periods of several months.

Finally, the cost of O&M for a WEC based on de Andres et al. (2014) is assessed. This cost was evaluated with different failure rates assuming failure like a random event along the year. For low failures rates some locations like Ireland show a low O&M cost per kWh. However, as failure rate get higher these sites have higher cost compared to milder sites (Spain or Portugal). In these terms some sites are found to have a good balance between power production and O&M cost. For instance, Scotland is characterized by a cost of 1.8 Eurocents/kWh and a power production of 130 kW. However, some locations like Australia or Chile are found to have very high O&M costs compared with other locations with power production not so high in percentage. Also another place that it is found to have a good balance between availability and resource was the coast of Nova Scotia with a resource of 25 kW/m and a cost for O&M of 1.2 Eurocents/kWh.

From this study it is also concluded that there are some sites with a very high resource, for instance the East coast of Ireland (55 kW/m) that are valid for mature technologies with low failure rates. However, for prototype testing when failures have a higher probability, milder locations are recommended (Spain, Portugal) because of a lower O&M costs for these failure rates.

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